

REVIEW ON PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF COUGH AND MARKETED DRUG PREPARATION USE FOR COUGH

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ABSTRACT

Coughing is an important defensive reflex and prevalent health issue, with syrups being a common over-the-counter treatment. It occurs through the stimulation of a complex reflex arc. The primary action of currently available cough suppressants (dextromethorphan, codeine) on central cough pathway.

KEYWORDS: Cough, anti-tussive, cough reflex arc, C-fibers, rapidly adapting receptor, slowly adapting receptors.

INTRODUCTION

Cough syrup is a liquid medication used to relieve cough and soothe the irritated throat by delivering active ingredients via oral intake. It is a term used for inflammation and fluid in the lungs caused by a bacterial, viral or fungal illness and cause difficulty in breathing.^[1] When your throat or airways becomes irritated, your body reacts by coughing and brain receives the signal from a nerve when they are irritated. Cough syrups work by suppressing the cough reflex (anti-tussives), thinning the mucus to make easier to cough up (expectorant), and soothing the throat (demulcent).^[2] Usually, diphenhydramine hydrochloride having the cough suppressant properties which suppresses the cough.^[3] Ammonium chloride used as expectorant helps to make thin and loosen phlegm (mucus) from the airways, making it easier to cough-up and sodium citrate act as mucolytic agent, helps to reduce congestion in the chest and the throat. This combination provides relief from coughing, allergy symptoms like runny nose and chest congestion.^[4]

Fig. 1.1: Stimulation of Cough.

History

The history of the cough syrup began with ancient origins where people were treating cough with traditional remedies like herbs, honey. In the 18th century, cough syrups consisted of mixtures of syrups, alcohol, and potent ingredients like opium were added reflecting the lack of regulation and advanced understanding of pharmacology at that time. Godfrey's Cordial was a well-known example of the 18th century cough syrup, it was considered as a popular remedy that contained opium and was also associated with many cases of fatal poisoning.^[5]

Advances in medicine in the 19th century shifted understanding of diseases, which paved the way for more sophisticated treatment, with Vicks developing effective, non-narcotic syrups in the 1950s. Physicians developed the formulation containing the cough suppressing properties of morphine and heroin. Though 19th century saw the major advancements in understanding disease, moving away from older theories like humorism towards a more scientific, pathological understanding.^[6]

The success of 20th century cough syrup was driven by the development of active cough suppressants like codeine and dextromethorphan, replacing with the earlier ineffective patent medicines. Codeine, an opioid derived from opium, was used in the cough syrups as an

effective suppressant but its use was limited due to its addictive properties and potential for respiratory depression.^[7] A Dextromethorphan (DXM) was a great success towards the pharmaceutical science.^[8] Its availability in over-the-counter formulations made it widely accessible and successful product. It is proved to be more effective, reliable cough suppressant and was safer than earlier remedies containing opiates or other any dangerous ingredients and moving towards effective and safe treatments. The 20th century has led to the successful transition from dangerous or ineffective remedies to modern pharmaceuticals.

The most recent development for cough syrup formulation include novel oral drugs like P2X3 receptor antagonist gefapixant, an investigational drug, for the treatment of refractory or chronic cough. Its development marks a new approach to targeting chronic cough by blocking specific receptors on sensory nerve fibers in the airway lining.^[9]

Types of cough

Cough can be differentiated as wet or dry cough. A wet cough that brings up the mucus or phlegm from the lungs and airways, indicating an infection like flu and thus it is productive cough whereas a dry cough do not produce any mucus and non-productive that many feel like tickle or irritation to the throat.

According to the type of duration, cough can be categorized in the three types:

- Acute cough: A cough lasts for 3 weeks or less and may cause due to short-term illness.
- Sub-acute: A cough last for 3-8 weeks.
- Chronic: A cough persists more than 8 weeks and it can be a sign of serious or long term lung condition.

Symptoms of Cough

- Breathing issues like wheezing, shortness of breath
- Chest discomfort
- Fatigue
- Chronic symptoms including runny nose, postnasal drip, hoarseness or change in voice.

Diagnosis of cough

Diagnosis of cough begins with detailed history of patient and specific tests which includes sputum testing, metacholine challenge testing, imaging examination like chest CT scan, X-

ray or spirometry and blood tests to detect the underlying cause. The duration, type and accompanying symptoms of the cough are crucial for the diagnosis.

Mechanism of cough reflex

A cough is a reflex action that expels air and particles from the airways to clear irritants like dust, mucus etc.^[16] It involves a complex neurophysiological process which coordinated by cough reflex arc, involving sensory nerves, a cough center in the brainstem and motor nerves controlling the muscles of respiration and the larynx.^[17] The mechanical events of a cough involves three phases

1. Inspiratory Phase: It begins with a deep breath and generates the volume necessary for an effective cough.
2. Compressive Phase: Closure of the larynx combined with the contraction of the abdominal and intercostal (rib) muscles, which builds the intrathoracic pressure exceed 300 mm Hg.
3. Expiratory Phase: The glottis opens, allowing the high pressure air to be forcefully expelled from the lungs at a high velocity, carrying mucus, debris or other irritants from airways.^[18]

Cough Reflex Arc

The cough reflex arc is constituted by

1] Afferent Pathway: Sensory nerve fibers such as C-fibers and rapidly adapting receptors (RARs) located in the ciliated epithelium of upper airway (pulmonary, pharyngeal, auricular, superior laryngeal, gastric) and cardiac and esophageal branches from the diaphragm are stimulated by the irritants like smoke, dust or pathogens. The afferent impulses send signals via the vagus nerve to medulla oblongata of the brainstem.

2] Cough Center: It is a central coordinating region is located in the upper brainstem and pons and responsible to produce a cough.

3] Efferent Pathway: The cough center sends signals down the vagus, phrenic, and spinal motor nerves to the diaphragm, abdominal wall, respiratory muscles and laryngeal muscles. These motor commands trigger the coordinated action of the muscles and larynx to complete the compressive and expiratory phases of the cough.^[19]

Airway afferent nerves are broadly classified by their conduction velocity, function and stimuli they respond to:

1] C-fibers: They are slow-conducting, unmyelinated fibers (diameter : 0.2-1.5 micrometer) many polymodal nonreceptors that is they respond to variety of stimuli like chemical, thermal and mechanical irritants playing a role in lingering, poorly localized sensation after a stimulus. They are found in the nerves of somatic sensory system.^[20] They transmit signals for dull pain, burning itch, temperature from body periphery to spinal cord and brain. C-fibers are grouped together called Remak bundles. These occur when a non-myelinating Schwann cells bundles the axon closes together by surrounding them. The Schwann cells keeps them from touching each other by squeezing its cytoplasm between axons. Example, in the rat model large bundles of greater than 20 axons found exiting L5 dorsal root ganglion, while smaller bundles of 3 axons found in distal nerve segments.

The spinothalamic tract is main pathway associated with the pain, temperature and perception.

Damage or injury to nerve fibers cause neuropathic pain. Capsaicin activates C-fibers vanilloid receptor, providing burning sensation. Vanilloid receptors are found on the free nerve endings of both A and C fibers respond to elevated heat levels (>43 deg C) and chemical capsaicin. VR1 respond to extracellular acidification and essential for inflammation sensitization to noxious thermal stimuli. Another type (TRP V2-VRL-1) Vanilloid-like receptor has higher threshold of activation regarding heat about 52 C and responds to capsaicin and low pH.^[30] Both types of receptors are transmembrane receptors that are closed during resting condition.

Functions of C-fibers

- Responsible to hypoxia, hypoglycemia, hyper-osmolality and light/sensitive touch.
- C-fibers include:
 - C fibers nociceptors responsible for burning pain.
 - C fiber warming specific receptor responsible for warmth.
 - Ultra flow histamine selective C-fibers responsible for itching.
 - Tactile C-fibers responsible for sensual touch for several seconds after stimuli.

2] A- fibers: A-fibers are fast conducting rapidly and slowly adapting mechanosensors that transmit signals quickly, responsible for rapid sensation like sharp pain. A fiber have myelin sheath that speeds up nerve impulse transmission through salutatory conduction.

A-fibers are classified into two types

I] Rapidly Adapting Receptors (RARs): RAR also called as phasic receptors, responds to onset and offset of a stimulus but decreasing the firing rate of stimulus remains constant. These receptors are vital for detecting changes in a stimulus and involved in the sensation like vibration, movement, flutter, pressure. RAR occur throughout the respiratory tract from the nose to the bronchi. They probably cause cough, the expiration reflex and other laryngeal reflexes such as cardiovascular, mucus secretion, bronchoconstrictor, and laryngoconstrictor.^[39] They are differentiated from other airways afferents by their rapid adaptation (1-2 seconds) to sustained lung inflations. Substances like bradykinin, histamine. Capsaicin, substance P activates RARs in a way that that can be markedly inhibited or abolished by preventing the local end-organ effects that these stimuli produce bronchospasm

and mucus secretion through parasympathetic pathways. Example of RARs is Meissner’s corpuscles found in the skin and responsible for detecting light touch, flutter and slip sensation.

II] Slowly Adapting Receptors (SARs)

SARs are also known as tonic receptors, a type of sensory receptor that continues to send a signals to the nervous system as long as stimulus is present, providing information about the duration of the stimulus. SARs are highly sensitive to the mechanical forces that are put on the lung during breathing. SARs activity increases during inspiration and peaks just prior to the initiation of the expiration. SARs may facilitate coughing by a central cough network via activation of the brainstem second order neurons of the SAR reflex pathway like slowly adapting pulmonary stretch that monitor lung inflation and receptors in the skin like Merkel’s discs and Ruffini corpuscles involved in detecting touch, pressure and stretch.

Drugs for cough

1] Pharyngeal demulcent: Demulcents are the soothing agents that coat the irritated mucus membrane of the throat to provide symptomatic relief from dryness and minor pain.^[10] They primarily act on the upper respiratory tract when administered orally, pharyngeal demulcent

mix with saliva to form a viscous, protective film over the pharynx and upper airway surfaces and this coating soothes irritation, provides lubrication and saliva flow.

2] Expectorant: They play an essential role in clearing the mucus from the airway, making easier to cough out phlegm and relieve chest congestion.^[11] They work by thinning and loosening the mucus, reducing its stickiness and widening the airways to make breathing easier. Bromohexine, ambroxol are active ingredients that can be combined with bronchodilators to further help with breathing.^[12]

3] Anti-tussives

- It acts as a cough suppressants, relieving dry, hacking coughs by inhibiting the cough reflex in the brain or suppressing cough impulses in the respiratory tract.^[13]

- Anti-tussives suppress cough by two main mechanism:

I] centrally acting agents- they inhibit cough center in the brain's brainstem.

Example, codeine centrally acting opioid anti-tussives suppresses cough reflex by binding to opioid receptor in CNS.

II] Peripherally acting agents- they directly inhibit cough impulses in the respiratory tract.^[14]

- Anti-histamines- It includes diphenhydramine used in the combination to relieve coughs, particularly caused by allergies and colds. Anti-histamines block histamine, a chemical that causes allergy symptoms and can trigger an irritating cough.^[15]

Marketed formulations

Following are some marketed formulations for wet cough:

1] Alex, Cofsils:

- Levosalbutamol
- Ambroxol
- Guaifenesin
- Menthol

2] Alkof Orange

- Guaifenesin
- Terbutaline
- Bromhexine

3] Ambtic, Koflid-Ax

- Ambroxol
- Terbutaline
- Guaifenesin
- Menthol

For dry cough

1] Alex, Norvent-D

- Dextromethorphan
- Chlorpheniramine
- Maleate
- Phenylephrine

2] Corex

- Codeine phosphate
- Maleate

3] Glycodin

- Dextromethorphan
- Menthol
- Terpin hydrate

Conclusion and In-future scope

This cough syrup seems useful and beneficial due to presence of active ingredient i.e. diphenhydramine HCl, which itself act as anti-histaminic and prevent allergic reactions. It is expected that the cough syrup industry will continue to grow in the years to come. This syrup formulation have many beneficial effects due to its content and its pharmacological properties, each ingredient have its individual desired effect to soothe the cough and provide relief from the infection. Other factors including product innovation, consumer will all influence the industry's development.

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